

STATIC BEHAVIOUR OF NANO-COMPOSITE REINFORCED CROSS-PLY LAMINATES VIA A MICROMECHANICS APPROACH

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SUMMARY: Bending behaviour of one dimensional structures is an important consideration in the design of structural components. In the present study a multiscale analysis of the deflection behaviour of carbon nanotube/polymer composite beams is presented. The micromechanics models used in the study include straight CNTs aligned in one direction, randomly oriented CTNs and a two parameter model of agglomeration. The effect of volume fraction of CNTs are investigated on the beam deflection and comparisons are made with carbon fibre reinforced composites. The main purpose of the study is to observe the stiffening effect of CNTs when used in small quantities which is the case presently due to cost considerations.

KEYWORDS: Carbon nanotube, micromechanics, nano composites, composite beams.

INTRODUCTION

The exceptional mechanical and physical properties of carbon nanotubes have been instrumental in the development of carbon nanotube-reinforced polymer composites since their invention in 1991 by Iijima [1]. Carbon nanotubes are known to provide an exceptional degree of stiffness and strength when used as a reinforcement material in fibre composites [2, 3]. The near perfect microstructure of nanotubes, which at the atomic scale can be thought of as a hexagonal sheet of carbon atoms rolled into a cylinder, gives them this exceptionally high stiffness and high strength. The outcome is that an order-of-magnitude increases in strength and stiffness relative to standard carbon-fibres can be achieved [4, 5]. The high strength-to-weight and high stiffness-to-weight ratios predicted for carbon nanotube-reinforced polymer (CNRP) materials could provide many opportunities for this new class of materials in weight-critical applications such as aerospace vehicles [6]. However, the full potential of carbon nanotubes as reinforcement has not been realized yet due to a number of factors. For example presently it is very difficult to align them straight in a matrix due to their slenderness, in particular, in large scale and suitable for commercial use [7]. They also tend to agglomerate due to atomic forces in play at the nano scale reducing the effectiveness of reinforcement due to heterogeneity.

For the implementation of CNRPs in structural applications, accurate property-microstructure relations are required in the form of micromechanics models. In present study three different micromechanics models are employed, namely, aligned, randomly oriented and agglomerated ones. The effects of the characteristics developed in these models are investigated on the performance of nano composite plates. Modelling of carbon nanotubes in a polymer matrix has been considered in a number of publications with the objective of establishing the properties of nanotube reinforced materials [8, 9]. However, the deflection behaviour of

structural components made of carbon nanotube reinforced plastics (CNRP) seems to be studied only for beams [10]. The present study extends this work to laminated plates.

BASIC EQUATIONS

We consider a simply supported laminated cross-ply plate of dimensions a and b in the x and y directions, respectively. The differential equation governing the behaviour of symmetrically laminated cross-ply plates under a distributed load $q(x, y)$ is given by

$$D_{11}w_{xxxx} + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})w_{xyyy} + D_{22}w_{yyyy} = q(x, y) \quad (1)$$

where D_{ij} are the bending stiffnesses, $w(x, y)$ is the deflection and the derivatives with respect to x and y are indicated by subscripts [11]. The boundary conditions for a simply supported plate are given by

$$-D_{11}w_{xx} - D_{12}w_{yy} = 0 \quad \text{at } x = 0, a \quad (2)$$

$$-D_{12}w_{xx} - D_{22}w_{yy} = 0 \quad \text{at } y = 0, a \quad (3)$$

The load acting on the plate can be expanded in Fourier sine series as

$$q(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} q_{mn} \sin \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y \quad (4)$$

where $\alpha_m = m\pi/x$ and $\beta_n = n\pi/y$ with the coefficients q_{mn} given by

$$q_{mn} = (4/ab) \int_0^b \int_0^a q(x, y) \sin \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y \, dx \, dy \quad (5)$$

The solution for deflection can be assumed in the following form

$$w(x, y) = \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_{mn} \sin \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y \quad (6)$$

which satisfies the boundary conditions (2) and (3). The coefficient C_{mn} is given by

$$C_{mn} = \frac{a^4 q_{mn}}{\pi^4 D_{mn}} \quad (7)$$

where

$$D_{mn} = D_{11}m^4 + 2(D_{12} + 2D_{66})(mnr)^2 + D_{22}(nr)^4 \quad (8)$$

with $r=a/b$ being the aspect ratio. The stresses σ_{xx}^k , σ_{yy}^k and τ_{xy}^k at the k -th layer are computed from

$$\sigma_{xx}^k = \frac{a^2}{\pi^2} \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{q_{mn}}{D_{mn}} (\bar{Q}_{11}^k m^2 + \bar{Q}_{12}^k n^2 r^2) \sin \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_{yy}^k = \frac{a^2}{\pi^2} z \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{q_{mn}}{D_{mn}} (\bar{Q}_{12}^k m^2 + \bar{Q}_{22}^k n^2 r^2) \sin \alpha_m x \sin \beta_n y \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_{xy}^k = -2 \frac{a^2}{\pi^2} r \bar{Q}_{66}^k z \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{q_{mn}}{D_{mn}} mn \cos \alpha_m x \cos \beta_n y \quad (11)$$

where \bar{Q}_{11}^k , \bar{Q}_{12}^k , \bar{Q}_{22}^k and the reduced stiffnesses of the k-th layer.

MICROMECHANICS MODELS

The effect of the nanotube reinforcement on the deflection behaviour of the plate is studied by determining the elastic properties of the material in terms of the fibre content. The elastic constants of the material can be expressed in terms of the fibre volume fraction using micromechanics relations. In the present study three different micromechanics models will be employed to investigate various types of composite materials. The first micromechanics model determines the elastic behaviour of CNRP reinforced with aligned nanotubes which are taken straight and continuous. A second model is applied to CNRPs reinforced with randomly oriented nanotubes. A third model is used to characterize CNRPs reinforced with randomly oriented nanotubes concentrated in agglomerations. Thus various types of reinforcements can be assessed and compared in terms of their effect on the plate stiffness.

Aligned Nanotubes

An elementary cell of a unidirectional composite material is taken with the axis of revolution in the fibre direction. The elastic behaviour of an elementary cell of the composite material can be expressed as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \sigma_{33} \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} n & l & l & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ l & k+m & k-m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ l & k-m & k+m & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2m & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2p & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 2p \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_{11} \\ \epsilon_{22} \\ \epsilon_{33} \\ \epsilon_{23} \\ \epsilon_{13} \\ \epsilon_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

where k , l , m , n , and p are the Hill's elastic moduli; n is the uniaxial tension modulus in the fibre direction (direction 1), k is the plane-strain bulk modulus normal to the fibre direction, l is the associated cross modulus, m and p are the shear moduli in planes normal and parallel to the fibre direction, respectively. A composite with a reinforcing phase volume fraction c_r , matrix Young's modulus E_m and matrix Poisson's ratio ν_m is considered. Using the Mori-Tanaka method, the Hill's elastic moduli are found to be [12]:

$$k = \frac{E_m \{E_m c_m + 2k_r (1 + \nu_m) [1 + c_r (1 - 2\nu_m)]\}}{2(1 + \nu_m) [E_m (1 + c_r - 2\nu_m) + 2c_m k_r (1 - \nu_m - 2\nu_m^2)]} \quad (13)$$

$$l = \frac{E_m \{c_m \nu_m [E_m + 2k_r (1 + \nu_m)] + 2c_r l_r (1 - \nu_m^2)\}}{(1 + \nu_m) [2c_m k_r (1 - \nu_m - 2\nu_m^2) + E_m (1 + c_r - 2\nu_m)]} \quad (14)$$

$$n = \frac{E_m^2 c_m (1 + c_r - c_m v_m) + 2c_m c_r (k_r n_r - l_r^2) (1 + v_m)^2 (1 - 2v_m)}{(1 + v_m) \{2c_m k_r (1 - v_m - 2v_m^2) + E_m (1 + c_r - 2v_m)\}} + \frac{E_m [2c_m^2 k_r (1 - v_m) + c_r n_r (1 - 2v_m + c_r) - 4c_m l_r v_m]}{2c_m k_r (1 - v_m - 2v_m^2) + E_m (1 + c_r - 2v_m)} \quad (15)$$

$$p = \frac{E_m [E_m c_m + 2(1 + c_r) p_r (1 + v_m)]}{2(1 + v_m) [E_m (1 + c_r) + 2c_m p_r (1 + v_m)]} \quad (16)$$

$$k = \frac{E_m [E_m c_m + 2m_r (1 + v_m) (3 + c_r - 4v_m)]}{2(1 + v_m) \{E_m [c_m + 4c_r (1 - v_m)] + 2c_m m_r (3 - v_m - 4v_m^2)\}} \quad (17)$$

where k_r , l_r , m_r , n_r and p_r are the Hill's elastic moduli for the reinforcing phase. The expressions for the moduli of the CNRP as functions of the stiffness constants are determined for a unidirectional composite as follows [12]:

$$E_L = n - \frac{l^2}{k}, \quad E_T = \frac{4m(kn - l^2)}{kn - l^2 + mn}, \quad G_{LT} = 2p, \quad \nu_{LT} = \frac{l}{2k} \quad (18)$$

Randomly Oriented Nanotubes

Shi *et al.* [12] derived expressions for the bulk modulus and shear modulus of a composite reinforced with randomly oriented, straight nanotubes using the Mori-Tanaka method. The bulk modulus K and shear modulus G were given as follows:

$$K = K_m + \frac{c_r (\delta_r - 3K_m \alpha_r)}{3(c_m + c_r \alpha_r)}, \quad G = G_m + \frac{c_r (\eta_r - 2G_m \beta_r)}{2(c_m + c_r \beta_r)} \quad (19)$$

where,

$$\alpha_r = \frac{3(K_m + G_m) + k_r - l_r}{3(G_m + k_r)} \quad (20)$$

$$\beta_r = \frac{1}{5} \left\{ \frac{4G_m + 2k_r + l_r}{3(G_m + k_r)} + \frac{4G_m}{G_m + p_r} + \frac{2[G_m(3K_m + G_m) + G_m(3K_m + 7G_m)]}{G_m(3K_m + G_m) + m_r(3K_m + 7G_m)} \right\} \quad (21)$$

$$\delta_r = \frac{1}{3} \left[n_r + 2l_r + \frac{(2k_r + l_r)(3K_m + 2G_m - l_r)}{G_m + k_r} \right] \quad (22)$$

$$\eta_r = \frac{1}{5} \left[\frac{2}{3} (n_r - l_r) + \frac{8G_m p_r}{G_m + p_r} + \frac{2(k_r - l_r)(2G_m + l_r)}{3(G_m + k_r)} + \frac{8m_r G_m (3K_m + 4G_m)}{3K_m (m_r + G_m) + G_m (7m_r + G_m)} \right] \quad (23)$$

K_m and G_m are the bulk and shear moduli of the matrix, respectively. The effective Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν of the material are given by:

$$E = \frac{9KG}{3K + G}, \quad \nu = \frac{3K - 2G}{6K + 2G} \quad (24)$$

Agglomeration of Randomly Oriented Nanotubes

It has been observed in carbon nanotube-reinforced composites that a large amount of the nanotubes are concentrated in agglomerates. A two parameter micromechanics model of agglomeration is used to determine the effect of nanotube agglomeration on the elastic properties of randomly oriented CNRP composites [12]. The total volume V_r of the nanotubes in the representative volume element V can be divided into the following two parts:

$$V_r = V_r^{inclusion} + V_r^m \quad (25)$$

where $V_r^{inclusion}$ and V_r^m denote the volumes of nanotubes dispersed in the inclusions and in the matrix, respectively. The two parameters used to describe the agglomeration are defined as

$$\xi = \frac{V_r^{inclusion}}{V}, \quad \zeta = \frac{V_r^{inclusion}}{V_r} \quad (26)$$

where ξ denotes the volume fraction of inclusions, $V_{inclusion}$, with respect to total volume of the composite V and ζ denotes the volume fraction of nanotubes in the inclusions with respect to the total volume of nanotubes. When $\xi=1$, the nanotubes are uniformly dispersed in the matrix, and with the decrease in ξ , the agglomeration degree increases. When $\zeta=1$, all the nanotubes are concentrated in the inclusions with the concentration of nanotubes in the inclusions decreasing with decreasing ζ . When $\xi=\zeta$, the nanotubes are uniformly distributed within the matrix and ζ must be greater than ξ for agglomeration to be present. The volume fractions of nanotubes in the inclusions and in the matrix are expressed respectively as:

$$\frac{V_r^{inclusion}}{V_{inclusion}} = \frac{c_r \zeta}{\xi}, \quad \frac{V_r^m}{V - V_{inclusion}} = \frac{c_r (1 - \zeta)}{1 - \xi} \quad (27)$$

The effective bulk moduli K_{in} and K_{out} and the effective shear moduli G_{in} and G_{out} of the inclusions and the matrix, respectively are calculated for randomly oriented nanotubes as

$$K_{in} = K_m + \frac{(\delta_r - 3K_m \alpha_r) c_r \zeta}{3(\xi - c_r \zeta + c_r \zeta \alpha_r)}, \quad K_{out} = K_m + \frac{c_r (\delta_r - 3K_m \alpha_r) (1 - \zeta)}{3[1 - \xi - c_r (1 - \zeta) + c_r (1 - \zeta) \alpha_r]} \quad (28)$$

$$G_{in} = G_m + \frac{c_r \zeta (\eta_r - 2G_m \beta_r)}{2(\xi - c_r \zeta + c_r \zeta \beta_r)}, \quad G_{out} = G_m + \frac{c_r (1 - \zeta) (\eta_r - 2G_m \beta_r)}{2[1 - \xi - c_r (1 - \zeta) + c_r (1 - \zeta) \beta_r]} \quad (29)$$

The effective bulk modulus K and the effective shear modulus G of the composite are derived for particulate composites as:

$$K = K_{out} \left[1 + \frac{\xi \left(\frac{K_{in}}{K_{out}} - 1 \right)}{1 + \alpha (1 - \xi) \left(\frac{K_{in}}{K_{out}} - 1 \right)} \right], \quad G = G_{out} \left[1 + \frac{\xi \left(\frac{G_{in}}{G_{out}} - 1 \right)}{1 + \beta (1 - \xi) \left(\frac{G_{in}}{G_{out}} - 1 \right)} \right] \quad (30)$$

with

$$\alpha = \frac{1 + \nu_{out}}{3(1 - \nu_{out})}, \quad \beta = \frac{2(4 - 5\nu_{out})}{15(1 - \nu_{out})} \quad (31)$$

The effective Young's modulus E and Poisson's ratio ν are again given by eq. (24).

STRUCTURAL APPLICATIONS

In the present study, classical laminate theory is used to analyse the performance of a symmetrically laminated CNRP plate under a uniformly distributed load. The results are compared to traditional carbon fibre-reinforced polymer composites.

Aligned Nanotube-Reinforced Laminate

The deflection at the centre of the plate w_c is computed for various volume fractions of the nanotubes c_r . To assess the performance of a nanotube-reinforced composite beam relative to fibre reinforced plastic beams, a comparison is made with a high modulus, high strength unidirectional carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy with the following characteristics:

$$E_{11}=159 \text{ GPa}, \quad E_{22}=14 \text{ GPa}, \quad G_{12}=4.8 \text{ GPa}, \quad \nu_{12}=0.32, \quad V_f=0.6, \quad \rho=1570 \text{ kg/m}^3$$

The decrease in deflection versus the increase in volume fraction of nanotubes for two stacking sequences is shown in Fig. 1 which shows deflection of the plate with respect to unreinforced polymer plate. It is observed that the deflection of the beam decreases dramatically at low volume fractions of nanotubes. This illustrates the substantial increase in stiffness of a CNRP plate with the addition of a small volume of nanotubes.

Figure 1. Curves of the deflection plotted against CNT volume fraction c_r for a plate with aspect ratio $a/b=2$.

Deflection of the CNRP plate with respect to unreinforced polymer plate for various nanotube radii are shown in Fig. 2 for an aspect ratio of $a/b=1$. The values of the elastic constants for SWNTs for different nanotube radii are taken from Popov *et al.* [13]. The effect of nanotube radius on the constitutive modelling has been studied in [14]. Fig. 2 indicates that smaller radii of nanotubes lead to stiffer plates with the deflection decreasing rapidly with increasing fibre volume ratio.

Figure 2. Curves of the deflection plotted against CNT volume fraction c_r for a plate with aspect ratio $a/b=1$ for various nanotube diameters.

Stress distribution within a square CNRP plate is shown in Fig. 3 for a nanotube volume fraction of $c_r = 0.1$.

Figure 3. Stress distribution in a square CNRP square plate with stacking sequence $(0/90/0/90)_s$.

Figure 4. Deflection contour lines for a CNRP square plate relative to a carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy plate

The contours of the deflection of a CNRP plate relative to a carbon fibre-reinforced epoxy plate are shown in Fig. 4 with respect to fibre volume fraction and the height h of the plate. It is observed that for equal height plates, i.e., $h=1$, 35% of CN reinforcement provides the same deflection as the carbon fiber reinforced plate.

Randomly Oriented Nanotubes

Cotourlines of the deflections and the mass of a CNRP plate with randomly oriented fibres are shown in Fig. 5 relative to the deflection and mass of a randomly oriented carbon fibre/nylon plate in terms of plate thickness and fibre volume ratio. It is observed that a small amount of carbon nanotube reinforcement reduces the deflection significantly for the same mass.

Figure 5. Deflection of CNRP plate with respect to an unreinforced plate for various nanotube radii (a) deflection (b) mass

Randomly Oriented Agglomerated Nanotubes

The effect of the agglomeration is shown in Fig. 6 where the contours of the relative deflections for agglomerated plate and a plate with uniform fibre distribution is shown. It is observed that as the level of agglomeration increases, the deflection also increases indicating the negative effect of agglomeration.

Figure 6. Deflection of agglomerated plate relative to the deflection of a plate with uniformly distributed fibres

CONCLUSIONS

The deflection behaviour of nano composite laminated plates was examined by using micromechanics relations to determine the elastic constants in terms of fibre volume fraction. Micromechanics models were employed for aligned and continuous nanotubes, randomly oriented tubes and agglomerated composites. The effect of various factors on the deflection behaviour was studied.

Aligned CNRP plates showed significant improvements over carbon fibre-reinforced polymers and it was observed that a small percentage of nanotube reinforcement led to significant improvements in plate stiffness. However, the structural performance of randomly oriented nanotubes was also superior to the corresponding carbon fibre/nylon plate reducing the deflections considerably for the same mass. The effect of nanotube radii on the stiffness was studied for aligned nanotubes and it was observed that smaller radii produce stiffer plates. A significant effect of nanotube agglomeration is to reduce the effectiveness of the reinforcement. This aspect was investigated by a contour diagram of deflections in terms of the two agglomeration parameters which indicate the level of dispersion of the nanotubes in the composite. The numerical results provide a quantitative assessment of the effect of various types of carbon nanotube reinforcements on the static behaviour of laminated plates.

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